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Nigeria State and Administration of Correctional Centres in Nigeria under Buhari Government: Issues and Prognoses

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Abstract

The Nigeria Correctional Services is saddled with the responsibilities of ensuring the development, maintenance and rehabilitation of the convicts using correctional facilities. Also, it has a responsibility to ensure security of the inmates and the entire facilities to avoid jail break. Incidentally, jailbreaks seem to have become a recurring incidence in Nigeria particularly under the Buhari administration. Such a worrisome trajectory appears to be linked to poor administration of the correctional services centres. Therefore, this paper examines the nexus between Nigeria state and administration of correctional centres under Buhari Government. The posits that the Nigerian correctional centres are poorly funded, understaffed, lack infrastructural facilities, overcrowded due to delay in justice system and also lack technology to effectively prevent jailbreak. It argues that under-utilization of intelligence and non-installation of surveillance gadgets seem to account for recurring jailbreaks in Nigeria. This has led to increase in insecurity manifest in insurgency, banditry, kidnapping and armed robbery that has continued to threaten the corporate existence of the Nigerian state. The paper is anchored on broken window theory as a framework of analysis. While relying on documentary approach by utilizing secondary sources of data and depended on content analysis. Paper revealed that under-utilization of intelligence and non-installation of surveillance gadgets in preventing crime by the Nigerian state increased incidences of jailbreak in Nigeria. Thus, it recommends among other things, the need for adequate and timely utilization of intelligence and installation of surveillance in the administration of correctional centres in Nigeria.

Keywords: Administration, Correctional centres, Intelligence, surveillance gadgets, and Jailbreaks

Introduction

To provide a rehabilitation and correctional facility for those who have broken social norms is the major objective of the jail institution on a global scale. Nigeria Prison Services (NPS), now known as the Correctional Services Centre (CSC), is in charge of the maintenance, development, and rehabilitation of inmates utilizing prison facilities in Nigeria. Following the construction of Lagos' Broad Street jail in 1872, this resulted in the creation of the first jail administration based on British practice. In 1876, the Supreme Court ordinance and the jail ordinance establishing prisons were both passed (Ogundipe 2006). As a result, the jail ordinance's implementation in 1876 marked the beginning of Nigeria's prison administration. Accordingly, the Nigerian Prison Act of 1972 outlines the objectives and focus of the Nigerian Prisons Service. Prisons are tasked with receiving people who are lawfully held, determining the causes of their behavior, and rehabilitating them so that they can contribute to society as contributing members.

In order to prevent unauthorized escape from the custody of the prison, this necessitates that the prisons be safe and effectively guarded. To do this, the prison's walls are frequently constructed in a sophisticated fashion with all the security elements. This prevents jailbreaks and ensures efficient prison administration. Since the return to democratic governance in 1999, there have been constant jailbreaks in Nigerian correctional facilities (Ripples Nigeria Report, 2017). Since the former president Muhammadu Buhari's administration assumed office on May 29, 2015, there have been more prison breaks, leading to the escape of around 6,611 prisoners from prisons in twelve (12) states of the federal republic, including the Federal Capital Territory. It is clear that the current situation has worsened security across the entire nation.

The recent attack on the Kuje Medium Custodial Center, which led to the release of 879 convicts, including 68 Boko Haram extremists, was the most important and concerning incident in Nigeria and all of Africa. According to academicians and security analysts like Matazu (2022), this and other jailbreak incidents in Nigeria have led the Nigerian government to claim that prison administration in the nation has not received enough attention. It may be argued that the government is not doing enough to prevent crime and fight insecurity. This is based on the claim that the relevant authorities frequently get intelligence about impending attacks on correctional facilities before to the invasion, but the prison officials take little to no action to stop them.

The foregoing suggests that poor prison administration is a trigger of jailbreak. This is evident in the under-utilization of intelligence and non-installation of surveillance gadgets by the administrators due to the nonchalant attitude of the Nigerian state towards security of lives and property. The seemingly total neglect of intelligence and lack of security monitoring devices such as surveillance tower, body scanner and closed circuit television (CCTV) by the prison administrators obviously account for the recurring incidences of jailbreak that has intensified insecurity in Nigeria. Between September 2015 and July 2022, there have been over 18 incidents of jailbreak that have resulted in the outflow of about 7000 inmates from various correctional centres across the country (Abba, 2022 & Ezobi, 2022). The consequence manifests is increasing rate of crime and other social vices such as banditry, kidnapping and armed robbery that has constituted a gridlock and continued to threaten the corporate existence of the Nigerian state.

Correctional facilities in Nigeria have recently been attacked by criminal and terrorists such as armed bandits, kidnapers, Boko Haram terrorists and ISWAP leading to several jailbreaks which have continued to intensify insecurity across the country due to escaped of over 6,000 inmates including bandits, kidnapers and terrorists that are forcefully integrated into the society. Consequently, this has not only increase crime, but has also jeopardized the peace and tranquility of the country that resulted to overstretch of the Nation's security architecture (Matazu, 2022).

Obviously, poor internal security management in Nigeria particularly under Buhari government seems to have contributed to the increasingly jailbreaks in Nigeria (Ossai, 2022). For instance, unknown gunmen attacked the Abolongo Correctional facility in Oyo town freeing about 907 inmates on 22nd October, 2021 most of whom were awaiting trial. Similarly, ISWAP claimed responsibility for Kuje correction facility attack and thereby releasing 879 inmates. As a result, criminals are returning to the society and could cause more havoc in society like killing of security personnel, destruction of Independent National Electoral Commission offices, police stations, correctional facilities and other government facilities. The implication is that there will be more terrorists, unknown gunmen, kidnapers and bandits roaming the streets and engaging in more crimes undetected. Consequently, this is a troublesome situation as Nigerians are being killed daily in their father's land without safety.

Over the previous eight years, the security situation in Nigeria has gotten worse. Each and every part of the nation is impacted. Research by Musa (2023) found that security-related incidents resulted in 59,279 fatalities between May 29, 2015, when former President Buhari took office, and May 18, 2023, before he handed over power. During the period from May 29, 2007, to May 28, 2015, there were 34,066 fewer such fatalities.

Researchers, security specialists, and social analysts have developed ideas to explain the causes of frequent jailbreaks worldwide and in Nigeria in particular. Scholars such as Omale (2013); Falayi and Ajaja (2018); Imam and Langa (2019); Onah, Adeniyi and Eneh (2019); Ojo (2021); Ajitogo (2021); Balsamo and Sisak (2021); Abiodun et al. (2021); Oyedeji (2022); Abba (2022) and Ezobi (2022) among others tend to explain the triggers of jailbreak based on the factors such as under-staffing of correctional centres, poor infrastructures, overcrowding in jails, bribery and corruption, prolong waiting for trial, abuse of basic rights of inmates, poor feeding, loose security and poor medical care. These scholars did not explain how poor administration particularly how under-utilization of intelligence and non-installation of surveillance gadgets accounts for recurring jailbreaks in Nigeria. This gap in literature, is what the paper intends to fill and by so doing contributes to knowledge. Therefore, this paper examines how poor administration of correctional centres account for recurring jailbreaks in Nigeria's fourth republic under the Muhammadu Buhari administration.

Conceptualizing Prison, Prison Administration and Jail breaks

A prison is a place that has been recognized by state law as such and created to ensure the detention and custody of individuals who have been accused or found guilty of violating the state's criminal laws. The Nigerian Prison Act of 2009 states that a prison is any place or building in Nigeria that the minister of internal affairs has declared to be one through an order published in the Federal Gazette, along with a description of the location's intended geographic area. Orakwe (2011) argues that a jail is a place that has been expressly recognized as such by state legislation and constructed to secure the confinement and custody of those who have been accused of breaking the state's laws or criminal code. In this study, prison, also known as Correctional Services Center, is to be understood as a place where those who are deemed by law to be social misfits are kept in custody with a view to keeping their behavior within acceptable bounds while also modifying and adjusting their general life for the better.

Prison Administration

Prisons are facilities that conduct dual functions of providing inmates with rehabilitation while also serving dual purposes of punishing offenders of national laws. Under state control, prison functions as both a jail or detention institution and a correctional facility. Therefore, prison administration refers to a variety of legal actions related to planning and managing prisons or other correctional facilities. Prison administrators are accountable for making sure that inmate supervision and care adhere to the law. The Controller-General of the Nigerian Prisons Service is at the top of the NPS's administrative hierarchy in Nigeria. The nation's prison system continues to be plagued by challenges like deteriorating prison infrastructure, overcrowding, and a large population of prisoners awaiting trial, subpar inmate care and treatment, and other associated problems. The Kuje jailbreak in July 2022 was a prime example of how carelessly the nation was managing its custodial facilities (Ariyo, 2023).

Jailbreaks

Jailbreaking is the act of a prisoner making an illegal or unauthorized getaway. Normally, when this occurs, authorities try to locate them again and return them to the persons who had originally detained them. According to Nigerian law, convicts who force their way out of a prison are committing a crime. Prison breaks can be facilitated through a variety of techniques. The most frequently used technique by those responsible for jail breaks in Nigeria is physical. The convicts have also been known to use weapons and occasionally explosives like dynamite to subdue the prison's armed guard and other officials, which has resulted in fatalities.

Theoretical Framework- Broken Windows Theory

The theoretical framework adopted for this study is Broken Windows theory by Wilson James and George Kelling developed in 1982. The physical and social aspects of disorder are primarily addressed by the broken windows theory. Physical disorder refers to the state of a community's physical environment, including the state of any vacant lots, adjacent properties, and structures. Contrarily, social disorder refers to a pattern of social behavior that is obvious to the public and is perceived by many people to be abnormal or inappropriate (Wilson & Kelling, 1982).

According to the argument, as long as there is disorder, there will be more crime because disorder is the root of all crime and if disorder were to be reduced or eradicated, significant crimes would not happen. The argument also suggested that residents who believe the region is unsafe are afraid since disruption is so common. According to this argument, crime leads to more disorder and crime, and vice versa.

Additionally, proponents of this idea argued that broken windows express complacency and a lack of enforcement of the law, which increases people's dread of crime and weakens societal norms, allowing for greater mischief. Wilson and Kelling (1982) claimed that it is crucial for the police to prevent disorder and petty crimes like purse snatching, assault, rape, and burglary in order to prevent disruption, which eventually leads to crime. For them, if broken window (crime) remains unrepaired or unchecked it becomes a 'norm', and breaking more windows (committing more crimes) becomes tolerable. To this theory, failure to prevent minor crimes encourages perpetration of more crime and vandalization of properties because disorder is indirectly connected to serious crime.

According to the argument, breaking windows (committing crime) will cause greater disorder in society, and as people perceive that violent crime is rising, they will become more scared of their community. A turnover of households will occur, with those who can emigrate being replaced by those who are not attached to the community, as a result of the heightened levels of fear, which will prohibit people from intervening in the neighborhood and preventing their use of public space. This will inevitably increase crimes such as armed robbery, kidnapping, banditry drug trafficking, prostitution, and other forms of social vices (Wilson & Kelling 1982).

The justification for the use of the broken windows theory in this paper hinges on the fact that social disorder increase criminal behaviour which causes crime, and crime causes further disorder and crime. Therefore, the recurring incidence of jailbreak in Nigeria is caused by deteriorated insecurity which further causes crime such as attacks on correctional centres leading to escape of thousands of inmates that has increased fear on the citizens.

Nigeria State and Poor Correctional Centres Administration in Nigeria

Additionally, the ISWAP attack on the Kuje correctional facility is a sign of Nigeria's inadequate security administration. Therefore, despite massive annual budgets allocated to the security sectors, subpar security management in Nigeria looks to be a cankerworm that has persisted (Ossai, 2022). Due to inadequate management, Nigeria's prison system has been unable to fulfill its planned role as a result of the aforementioned circumstances, which appear to have had a negative influence on both prisoners and the general prison population. The jail system in Nigeria obviously lacks even the most fundamental human decency, as evidenced by the crippling, demeaning, and destructive conditions there. The prisons' statutory duty is to reform the prisoners and get them ready for a life without crime once their sentences are up. In fact, inadequate management of correctional facilities, which is evident in years of infrastructure deterioration, neglect of prisons in all its manifestations, including a lack of funding, has succeeded in turning jails into havens for criminals. Ineffective prison rehabilitation programs combined with the issues of the already overcrowded prisons act as a stimulus for jailbreaks in Nigeria.

Poor prison administration in Nigeria have been evidenced in number of conditions, including: overcrowding of the prisons, bonding by inmates due to long stay, inadequate rehabilitation programmes, under-utilization of intelligence, lack of surveillance gadgets, corruption and compromise of the prison officials as well as poor funding of the prison services.

i. Overcrowding and Congestion of the prisons: According to easily accessible information from the federal interior ministry, Nigeria's prisons are overcrowded. The jails are generally overcrowded with criminals imprisoned in dirty, small cells without enough food, water, or medical care. Additionally, illness outbreaks, environmental deterioration, and a high mortality rate are frequently present. To this aim, Omale (2013) listed a number of factors that contribute to jailbreaks, including overcrowding in jails, depriving inmates of certain perceived rights and privileges, poor medical care, inmate and staff trafficking, and a lack of friendly relationships among staff.

The amount of oxygen is significantly diminished when 100 individuals share a space designed for four. The stifling environment produces microscopic organisms, which in turn propagate diseases. In turn, this puts the lives of both staff and inmates in danger, causes the court's justice to be delayed unnecessarily, locks up insane individuals who are likely to hurt themselves or others if left untreated, and improperly ventilates cells, particularly the cell used for awaiting trials. Similarly, Ojo (2021) posits that poor living conditions of inmates due to lack of sanitation is a factor that triggers jailbreak. According to Daramola (2023), 52,446 of the 75,436 people detained nationwide are waiting for trial, which is straining the prisons' capacity.

ii. Bonding by inmates due to long stay: Because remand detainees are presumed innocent until proven guilty under the law, prisons are primarily used to treat convicted criminals. If these people are kept in detention for so long without going through a trial, the purpose of imprisonment is defeated. In addition, putting someone in detention for that long in filthy, congested conditions has a number of detrimental repercussions that may be criminological, sociological, physiological, economic, sociological, psychological, and more.

iii. Inadequate rehabilitation programmes and poor welfare of the inmate: A jail is not exactly supposed to be a bed of flowers, nor is it supposed to be a bed of thorns and thistles intended to suffocate the inmates—convicts are there for criminal purposes. According to Ogundipe (2006), Nigerian prison facilities work to ensure inmates' welfare by offering proper medical treatment, food, clothing, and recreational amenities in order to foster an environment that is conducive to reformation and rehabilitation programs. The government, who is supposed to be their welfare provider, has failed to supply them with the necessary welfare packages. Unfortunately, the Nigeria Correctional Services Centers have been described to "human cages with no facilities for correction, reformation, and vocational training" (Ahire, 1990). The stated goals of reformation and rehabilitation are not in harmony with the actual operating reality of the prison system. It has been contended that the stated goals of reformation and rehabilitation can scarcely be achieved given the punishing, deprived, and demeaning conditions of Nigerian prisons. This situation frequently encourages convicts to attempt prison escapes.

iv. Under-utilization of Intelligence: It is impossible to overstate the importance of intelligence and monitoring in the 21st century for reducing crime and maintaining security. This is due to the fact that intelligence and surveillance ensure a forward-looking and proactive approach to controlling insecurity and reducing crime, including organized transnational threats like terrorism, armed banditry, insurgency, and others that have propelled intelligence and surveillance from being concepts to strategies to addressing a variety of issues of

national security. Intelligence is obtained when information is believed to constitute a threat to a nation, its infrastructure, its people, interests, or the use of weapons of mass devastation.

Intelligence's main goal is to spot threats before they materialize and report them to the appropriate authority, which then takes preventative action to stop such occurrences from happening. The authorities in Nigeria appear to be constantly told about a variety of potential jailbreaks in advance, but they don't seem to do much to prevent them. According to research by Ripples Nigeria (2017), such plans are routinely reported to the office of the Controller General by the service's intelligence personnel at least a week or two prior to their execution. However, these intelligence reports are frequently disregarded or underused. The misuse of intelligence reports results in successful attacks and jailbreaks. Security experts claim that the underuse of intelligence reports appears to be deliberate. This seems to be a plan to protect their agent, the prison officer in command, while they keep getting paid. Additionally, this is done to ensure that the government has a need to allocate additional funds for the prison (Ripples Nigeria, 2017).

v. Lack of Surveillance gadgets: Lack of efficient monitoring instruments, such as surveillance towers, body scanners, closed-circuit television (CCTV), double perimeter walls, and other means of limitation to protect, control, and secure correctional facilities. One could argue that the lack of surveillance equipment or its improper installation serve to conceal criminal activity and corrupt behavior across Nigeria's prisons. All illegal activities and unethical behavior by Nigeria Prison Services workers would be exposed by the installation of monitoring devices. Surveillance equipment would tell you of what was occurring and how it all occurred. An investigation and/or an arrest may be made using the information from the surveillance.

In the absence of surveillance technology, there would be no records of events other than oral history, which portends danger. That the Kuje medium security center lacks a closed-circuit television (CCTV) system that can provide you analyses and record events was made clear by the former Senate President, Ahmad Lawan. According to him, the fact that there is no CCTV in a facility of this scale in the Federal Capital Territory of Abuja (FCT) proves that there are no CCTVs in any other medium security detention facilities across the country (Ripples Nigeria, 2022).

vi. Corruption and compromise of the prison officials: The cabal and their lieutenants have an organized corruption scheme that affects the convicts indirectly. Numerous prisoners imprisoned for serious crimes like armed robbery, kidnapping, murder, drug abuse, and human trafficking have been found to be smoking and dealing Indian hemp right inside the prison yards. Once more, the amount of money a prospective officer will pay determines whether or not they will be posted to sensitive positions around the nation as senior officers of the jails, not their ability to perform their jobs well. A practice that has corrupted the majority of the staff members in charge of the prison yards and led to poor meals for convicts, careless money extortion from inmates, poor facility maintenance, and flagrant violations of prison rules. Oyediji (2022) and Onah et al.'s (2019) claimed that these have strengthened jailbreaks and weakened the management and operations of Nigeria's prison system.

Also, the appointment and advancement of men and women in the prison services may have involved nepotism as a contributing element. Some of these connected officials are engaged in the trade of undermining law and order (Agbakwuru et al., 2021). In Nigeria, these officials have godfathers and are never held accountable or subjected to investigations. They are instead elevated to greater positions. The absence of proper facilities and the open theft of prisoners' rights, such as subpar nutrition, bad cleanliness, and extortion, make the situation in the jails even less secure. These pressures apply to offenders (Agbakwuru et al., 2021). Unfairness is connected to yet another factor. There are too many people being held in detention while awaiting the start or end of their trials. Prisoners experience desperation and are more open to suggestions of an early release.

vii. Poor Funding of the Prison Services and decaying infrastructure: Inadequate prison budget by the federal government hinders effective prison administration in Nigeria and, as a result, encourages jailbreak. Many prisons in Nigeria still have deteriorated buildings. There are not many jail vehicles available to bring prisoners to court for trials, and the facility's cells are already crowded. Since the majority of jail buildings in the country were constructed in the 19th century by the British colonial masters, many of them are outdated and in poor condition. For instance, the 1816, 1820, 1827, and 1831 respectively built Azare, Bauchi, Ningi, and Misau prisons are all located in Bauchi State. However, little to no action has been taken to address the institutional problems and infrastructure gaps. In Nigeria, jailbreaks are frequently encouraged by a lack of infrastructure, understaffed correctional facilities, and insufficient worker compensation.

Recurring Jailbreaks under Buhari's Administration 2015-2023

The prevailing incidences of jailbreaks in some Nigerian correctional centres have inflated anxiety and fear among the populace because of the security implication for the citizens and the nation at large. Between September 2015 and July 2022, Nigeria has experienced twenty-one (21) incidences of attacks on correctional

centres in several states such as Abia, Kogi, Ekiti, Ondo, Niger, Bauchi, Yobe, Delta, Ebonyi, Plateau, Akwa Ibom, Oyo, Edo, Imo, Enugu and FCT leading to the escaped of about 6,711 inmates. Out of the twenty-one (21) incidences of jailbreak across Nigerian correctional centres, thirteen (13) were successful while eight (8) were unsuccessful.

Similarly, states like Edo which attack on the Benin and Oko custodial facility occurred on the 19 October, 2020 recorded the highest number of escaped inmates totaling 1,993, followed by attack on Owerri custodial centre in Imo state on 4th April, 2021 with a total of 1,844 escapees. Invasion of Abolongo correctional centre in Oyo state took place on 22nd October 2021 with 907 escapees, and attack on Kuje correctional centre which took place on 6th July, 2022 has a total of 879 escapees. While incursion on Jos correctional centre in Plateau state happened twice on different occasion, 19th July, 2021 and 28th November, 2021 respectively, with a total of 524 escapees. These and other incidences of jailbreak across Nigerian correctional centres have intensified insecurity and increased other forms of social vices due to forceful released of inmates. This scenario is inimical to national security. Below is the tabular representation of incidences of jailbreak across Nigerian correctional centres.

Table 1. Showing Incidences of Jailbreak in Nigeria between 2015 and 2022

S/N	Correctional Centre Location	State	No. of Escaped Inmates	Date
1	Afokon	Calabar	0	2n September, 2015
2	Kuje	FCT Abuja	2	24 th June, 2016
3	Koto-Karfe	Kogi	13	29 th July, 2016
4	Nsukka	Enugu	15	8 th August, 2016
5	Abakaliki	Ebonyi	0	18 th August, 2016
6	Ikot-Ekpene	Akwa Ibom	36	27 th December, 2017
7	Minna	Niger	200	3 rd June, 2018
8	Benin & Oko	Edo	1,993	19 th October, 2020
9	Okitipupa	Ondo	58	22 nd October, 2020
10	Warri	Delta	0	22 nd October, 2020
11	Ajara Umudu	Abia	0	22 nd October, 2020
12	Ikoyi	Lagos	0	22 nd October, 2020
13	Owerri	Imo	1,844	4 th April, 2021
14	Bauchi	Bauchi	0	9 th April, 2021
15	Ubiaja	Edo	0	15 th April, 2021
16	Kurmawa	Kano	0	22 nd April, 2021
17	Jos	Plateau	262	19 th July, 2021
18	Kabba	Kogi	240	12 th September, 2021
19	Abolongo	Oyo	907	22 nd October, 2021
20	Jos	Plateau	262	28 th November, 2021
21	Kuje	FCT Abuja	879	6 th July, 2022

Source: Authors' Compilation with data from Chioma (2022)

From the above table, of the twenty-one (21) incidences of jailbreak in Nigeria between September 2015 and July 2022, thirteen (13) representing 80% were successful; while eight (8) representing 20% were unsuccessful. Similar to this, a total of six thousand seven hundred and eleven (6, 711) prisoners managed to escape from various prisons located in twelve (12) states of the federation, including the Federal Capital Territory, which serves as the seat of government for Nigeria. This has not only increased insecurity in the country, but has also threatened the existence of the Nigerian state. Due to the prison break and inability to apprehend the escapees, suggest that they may have moved into the forests as bandits, raising the possibility that they are to be blame for the killings in Kaduna, Sokoto, Niger, Zamfara and other locations (Habib, 2023). It is a worrisome trajectory.

However, the fact that prisons, where suspects and criminals were formally taken into custody, have subsequently turned into sources of internal security threat, suggests that there is a nationwide issue. Therefore, it is more troubling that we now have convicts who are more intelligent and brave than those who were employed to keep and rehabilitate them. Additionally, individuals outside prison walls who are determined to escape some inmates have developed stronger capabilities than the security system surrounding the prison walls (Jailbreaks and National Security, 2022). Therefore, the decline in the level of national security in Nigeria coincided however,

with the wave of recurring jailbreaks and as such has resulted in the rise of extremists' violence, kidnappings, and unknown killings by gunmen and among others.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Nigerian correctional centres have recently experienced incessant incursion leading to several jailbreaks that have resulted in the escaped of thousands inmates which has eventually intensified insecurity and increased other forms of social vices. However, this paper found that the trigger of recurring incidence of jailbreak in Nigeria is the under-utilization of intelligence and non-installation of surveillance by the Nigerian state in preventing crime and combating insecurity. Therefore, this paper recommended that:

(i). There should be timely and adequate utilization of intelligence as well provision of effective monitoring devices such as surveillance towers, body scanners, Close-Circuit Television (CCTV), double perimeter walls and other tools of restriction to protect, control and safeguard correctional facilities.

(ii). To improve surveillance, monitoring, intelligence collection, security, and protection of correctional facilities, there should be a fully armed squads, intelligence, and investigation unit.

(iii). Improved staffs salaries and emolument could curb corruption in the administration of correctional centres leading to recurrent incidences of jailbreak due to collusion between inmates and staffs.

References

Abba, A. (2022). Prison break: Tracking 18 incidents of jailbreaks under President Buhari. Retrieved from <https://www.icirnigeria.org/prison-break-tracking-18-incidents-of-jailbreaks-under-president-buhari/> Accessed on 31 August, 2022.

Agbakwuru, O., Nnochiri, I. & Ojelu, H. (2021). Insecurity: F.G under attack over 3,906 fleeing inmates. Retrieved from <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2021/11/insecurity-fg-under-attack-over-3906-fleeing-inmates/>. Accessed on 12th September, 2023.

Abiodun, T. F., Akinlade, M. T., Onyi, A. B., & Daramola, A. A. (2021). Recurrent waves of jailbreak in Nigeria: The imperatives of prison intelligence and dynamic security strategies in managing the Nigerian correctional facilities. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 8(5), pp.229-250

Ahire, P.T (1990). The Nigeria prison system: A social history. A paper presented at the national seminar on prison reform in Nigeria, Abuja.

Ariyo, I. (2023). Prison administration in Nigeria and threats of jail breaks. Retrieved from <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2023/01/prison-administration-in-nigeria-and-threats-of-jail-breaks/>. Accessed on 11th September, 2023.

Ayitogo, N. (2021). Analysis: Why jailbreaks have become commonplace in Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/headlines/499264-analysis-why-jailbreaks-have-become-commonplace-in-nigeria.html>. Accessed on 14 August, 2022.

Balsamo, M & Sisa, M. (2021). Prison break: 29 inmates escape federal lockups in 18 months. Retrieved from <https://apnews.com/article/government-and-politics-prisons-prison-breaks-business-c1979d6ad6e7b3531968dab0e61eb22d>. Accessed on 15 August, 2022.

Daramola, K. (2023). Aregbesola: States now empowered by law to build, manage correctional centres. Retrieved from: <https://www.thecable.ng/aregbesola-states-now-empowered-by-law-to-build-manage-correctional-centres>. Accessed on 10th September, 2023.

Ezeobi, C. (2022). Prison breaks in Nigeria, a ticking time bomb. Retrieved from <https://www.thisdaylive.com/index.php/2022/07/11/prison-breaks-in-nigeria-a-ticking-time-bomb/> Accessed on 24th January, 2023.

Falayi, K. & Ajaja, T. (2018). Nigerian prison cells where inmates live like kings, use co-prisoners as servants. Retrieved from <https://punchng.com/nigerian-prison-cells-where-inmates-live-like-kings-use-co-prisoners-as-servants/>. Accessed on 15 August, 2022.

Habib, G. (2023). Imo jailbreak: 864 convicted murderers, rapists still on the run. Retrieved from <https://punchng.com/imo-jailbreak-864-convicted-murderers-rapists-still-on-the-run/>. Accessed on 14 September, 2023.

Imam, H.I & Langa, S.A. (2019). Sociological analysis of the causes and effects of prison jail break in Kuje Medieum Security Prison, Kuje, FCT Abuja, Nigeria. *Abuja Journal of Sociological Studies*, 6(2). 174-192.

Matazu, H.K. (2022). Jailbreaks: 6,108 escapees threaten Nigeria's war against terror. Retrieved from <https://dailytrust.com/jailbreaks-6108-escapees-threaten-nigerias-war-against-terror>. Accessed on 20 August, 2022.

Musa, Y.S. (2023). Nigeria's security situation has got worse: what Tinubu's administration needs to do about it. Retrieved from <https://theconversation.com/nigerias-security-situation-has-got-worse-what-tinubus-administration-needs-to-do-about-it-206545>. Accessed on 11th September, 2023.

Nigerian Prisons Service Manual, (2009). Nigerian prisons service. Abuja, Nigeria.

Ogundipe, O. A. (2006). Prospect for the platform of prisons in democratic Nigeria: The need for reform. A Bulletin of the Nigerian Prisons Service.

Ogundipe, O. A. (2009). Prospect for the platform of prisons in democratic Nigeria, The reformer: A theoretical explanation. International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, 9(10). 93-97. bulletin of the Nigerian Prisons Service.

Ojo. J. (2021). Solutions to serial jailbreaks in Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://punchng.com/solutions-to-serial-jailbreaks-in-nigeria/>. Accessed on 15 August, 2022.

Omale, D.J. (2013). Riots/Jail breaks in Nigeria prisons: An aetiological study. Canadian Social Science, 9(1). 158-164.

Onah, O.O., Adeniyi, O. T. & Eneh, M.K. (2019). Increasing cases of prison break in Nigeria.

Orakwe, I.W. (2011). Strategies for the attainment of prison reform within the content of the proposed criminal justice reforms. Journal of Nigerian Prison Service Reformer, 5(1), 81-100.

Oroleye, A. K. (2018). Challenges of welfare administration of inmates in Nigeria prison system in SouthWestern Nigeria. International Journal of Politics and Good Governance Volume IX, (9); pp. 1-10

Ossai, N. (2022). Jailbreak in Nigeria: Causes, conditions, challenges and list of prisons. Retrieved from <https://www.skabash.com/jailbreak-in-nigeria/>. Accessed on 23rd January, 2023.

Oyedepi, O. (2022). As Nigeria Experiences its 20th Jailbreak in 7 Years, Here are Four Issues of Concern. Retrieved from <https://www.dataphyte.com/latest-reports/development/as-nigeria-experiences-its-20th-jailbreak-in-7-years-here-are-four-issues-of-concern/>. Accessed on 13 August, 2022.

Ripples Nigeria Report (2017). Nigerian Prisons of Scams and Corruption,. Retrieved from www.ripplesnigeria.com. Accessed on 20 August, 2022.

Ripples Nigeria Report (2022). Lawan decries lack of CCTV in Kuje prison after ISWAP attack. Retrieved from www.ripplesnigeria.com. Accessed on 31 August, 2022.

Wilson, J.Q., and Kelling, G.L. (1982). Broken Windows: The Atlantic Monthly (March) 249(3); 29-38. Retrieved from <http://www.personal.psu.edu/users/e/x/exs44/597b-Comm&Crime/Wilson-Kelling-Broken%20Windows.pdf> Accessed on 10 September, 2022.